

Supplementary Proofs for “Spatial Power Estimation via Riemannian Covariance Matching”

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This document provides the complete derivations and proofs corresponding to the section “Theoretical Analysis of the Matching Criteria” in our manuscript “Spatial Power Estimation via Riemannian Covariance Matching,” currently under review at the *IEEE Open Journal of Signal Processing*. For completeness, we restate the relevant definitions and theorems before presenting the proofs.

This document introduces no new results; its sole purpose is to provide detailed derivations and proofs that were omitted from the main paper due to space limitations.

1 Context

Throughout this note we adopt the notation from the main paper. In particular, we define the matrix

$$\mathbf{Q} \triangleq \mathbf{R}^{-1/2} \widehat{\mathbf{R}} \mathbf{R}^{-1/2} \in \mathcal{P}_M, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{R} \in \mathcal{P}_M$ is the model covariance, $\widehat{\mathbf{R}} \in \mathcal{P}_M$ is the sample covariance, and \mathcal{P}_M is the cone of $M \times M$ Hermitian positive definite matrices.

The examined criteria - AMV, SPICE, AIRM and JBLD- can be expressed as a sum of M scalar functions of the eigenvalues of \mathbf{Q} , $\{\lambda_m\}_{m=1}^M$:

$$\mathcal{D}_{\bullet}^2(\mathbf{R}, \widehat{\mathbf{R}}) = \sum_{m=1}^M \psi_{\bullet}(\lambda_m), \quad (2)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{\text{AMV}}(\lambda) &= (\lambda - 1)^2, & \psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda) &= \left(\sqrt{\lambda} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}}\right)^2, \\ \psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda) &= (\log \lambda)^2, & \psi_{\text{JBLD}}(\lambda) &= \log\left(\frac{1+\lambda}{2\sqrt{\lambda}}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

2 Derivation of ψ functions

AIRM.

We would like to show that $\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda) = (\log \lambda)^2$. From $\mathcal{D}_{\text{AIRM}}^2(\mathbf{R}, \widehat{\mathbf{R}}) = \|\log(\mathbf{Q})\|_F^2$, this is immediate.

AMV.

We would like to show that $\psi_{\text{AMV}}(\lambda) = (\lambda - 1)^2$. From $\mathcal{D}_{\text{AMV}}^2(\mathbf{R}, \widehat{\mathbf{R}}) = \|\mathbf{Q} - \mathbf{I}\|_F^2$, this is immediate.

SPICE.

We would like to show that $\psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda) = \left(\sqrt{\lambda} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}}\right)^2$. Notice that

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{D}_{\text{SPICE}}^2(\mathbf{R}, \widehat{\mathbf{R}}) &= \|\mathbf{R}^{-\frac{1}{2}}(\mathbf{R} - \widehat{\mathbf{R}})\widehat{\mathbf{R}}^{-\frac{1}{2}}\|_F^2 \\
&= \text{tr}\left(\mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{R} - \widehat{\mathbf{R}})\widehat{\mathbf{R}}^{-1}(\mathbf{R} - \widehat{\mathbf{R}})\right) \\
&= \text{tr}\left((\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{R}^{-1}\widehat{\mathbf{R}})(\widehat{\mathbf{R}}^{-1}\mathbf{R} - \mathbf{I})\right) \\
&= \text{tr}(\widehat{\mathbf{R}}^{-1}\mathbf{R}) + \text{tr}(\mathbf{R}^{-1}\widehat{\mathbf{R}}) - 2M.
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Since $\text{tr}(\mathbf{R}^{-1}\widehat{\mathbf{R}}) = \text{tr}(\mathbf{Q})$ and $\text{tr}(\widehat{\mathbf{R}}^{-1}\mathbf{R}) = \text{tr}(\mathbf{Q}^{-1})$, we can write (4) by

$$\mathcal{D}_{\text{SPICE}}^2 = \text{tr}(\mathbf{Q}) + \text{tr}(\mathbf{Q}^{-1}) - 2M = \sum_{m=1}^M (\lambda_m + \lambda_m^{-1} - 2). \tag{5}$$

Finally, for each $\lambda > 0$,

$$\lambda + \lambda^{-1} - 2 = \left(\sqrt{\lambda} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}}\right)^2,$$

hence the per-eigenvalue contribution is

$$\psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda) = \left(\sqrt{\lambda} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}}\right)^2.$$

JBLD.

We would like to show that $\psi_{\text{JBLD}}(\lambda) = \log\left(\frac{1+\lambda}{2\sqrt{\lambda}}\right)$. Observe that

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{D}_{\text{JBLD}}^2(\mathbf{R}, \widehat{\mathbf{R}}) &= \log\left|\frac{\mathbf{R} + \widehat{\mathbf{R}}}{2}\right| - \frac{1}{2}\log|\mathbf{R}\widehat{\mathbf{R}}| \\
&= \log|\mathbf{R} + \widehat{\mathbf{R}}| - \frac{1}{2}\log|\mathbf{R}\widehat{\mathbf{R}}| - M\log(2) \\
&= \log|\mathbf{I} + \widehat{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{R}^{-1}| + \log|\mathbf{R}| - \frac{1}{2}\log|\widehat{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{R}^{-1}| - \frac{1}{2}\log|\mathbf{R}^2| - M\log(2) \\
&= \log|\mathbf{I} + \widehat{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{R}^{-1}| - \frac{1}{2}\log|\widehat{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{R}^{-1}| - M\log(2).
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Now, using the fact that determinant is invariant under matrix similarity, and $\widehat{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{R}^{-1}$ is similar to \mathbf{Q} , we can write:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{D}_{\text{JBLD}}^2(\mathbf{R}, \widehat{\mathbf{R}}) &= \sum_{m=1}^M (\log(1 + \lambda_m) - \frac{1}{2}\log(\lambda_m) - \log(2)) \\
&= \sum_{m=1}^M \log\left(\frac{1 + \lambda_m}{2\sqrt{\lambda_m}}\right),
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

which concludes the derivation of ψ function for all criteria.

3 Proof of Theorem 1 (Asymptotic equivalence of criteria)

Theorem 1 (Asymptotic equivalence of criteria). *Let $\widehat{\mathbf{R}}$ be the sample covariance from N snapshots. Given a target $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, confidence $1 - \delta$, and radius $\rho \in (0, \log(1 + \varepsilon))$, if*

$$N \geq N_0(\varepsilon, \delta, \rho) := \frac{\kappa(\bar{\mathbf{R}})^2 e^{2\rho}}{(\varepsilon - (e^\rho - 1))^2} \left(M + \log(2/\delta) \right),$$

then with probability at least $1 - \delta$, for every $\mathbf{R} \in \mathcal{B}_{\text{AIRM}}(\bar{\mathbf{R}}, \rho)$ we have

$$\|\widehat{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{R}^{-1} - \mathbf{I}\|_2 \leq \varepsilon,$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{D}_{\text{AMV}}^2(\mathbf{R}, \widehat{\mathbf{R}}) - \mathcal{D}_{\text{SPICE}}^2(\mathbf{R}, \widehat{\mathbf{R}})| &\leq M \cdot C_{\text{AMV}}(\varepsilon) \varepsilon^3, \\ |\mathcal{D}_{\text{AIRM}}^2(\mathbf{R}, \widehat{\mathbf{R}}) - \mathcal{D}_{\text{SPICE}}^2(\mathbf{R}, \widehat{\mathbf{R}})| &\leq M \cdot C_{\text{AIRM}}(\varepsilon) \varepsilon^4, \\ |8\mathcal{D}_{\text{JBLD}}^2(\mathbf{R}, \widehat{\mathbf{R}}) - \mathcal{D}_{\text{SPICE}}^2(\mathbf{R}, \widehat{\mathbf{R}})| &\leq M \cdot C_{\text{JBLD}}(\varepsilon) \varepsilon^4, \end{aligned}$$

where $C_{\text{AMV}}, C_{\text{AIRM}}, C_{\text{JBLD}}$ are functions of ε that converge to finite constants as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$.

In particular, as $N \rightarrow \infty$ and $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, all criteria become equivalent in a neighborhood of the shared minimizer $\mathbf{R} = \widehat{\mathbf{R}}$.

Proof.

Let us first bound $\|\widehat{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{R}^{-1} - \mathbf{I}\|_2$ by a sum of two terms: model mismatch and sampling error.

Write

$$\|\widehat{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{R}^{-1} - \mathbf{I}\|_2 \leq \|\bar{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{R}^{-1} - \mathbf{I}\|_2 + \|(\widehat{\mathbf{R}} - \bar{\mathbf{R}})\mathbf{R}^{-1}\|_2. \quad (8)$$

Denote the r.h.s of (8) by ε . For $\mathbf{R} \in \mathcal{B}_{\text{AIRM}}(\bar{\mathbf{R}}, \rho)$, the generalized eigenvalues of $(\mathbf{R}, \bar{\mathbf{R}})$ lie in $[e^{-\rho}, e^\rho]$, hence

$$\|\bar{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{R}^{-1} - \mathbf{I}\|_2 = \|\mathbf{S}^{-1} - \mathbf{I}\|_2 \leq e^\rho - 1, \quad (9)$$

$$\|\mathbf{R}^{-1}\|_2 \leq \|\bar{\mathbf{R}}^{-1}\|_2 \|\mathbf{S}^{-1}\|_2 \leq \|\bar{\mathbf{R}}^{-1}\|_2 e^\rho, \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{S} := \bar{\mathbf{R}}^{-1/2} \mathbf{R} \bar{\mathbf{R}}^{-1/2}$. For Gaussian samples, the spectral concentration inequality ([1], see Theorem 4.7.1 or Exercise 4.7.3) yields, with probability $\geq 1 - \delta$,

$$\|\widehat{\mathbf{R}} - \bar{\mathbf{R}}\|_2 \leq \|\bar{\mathbf{R}}\|_2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{M + \log(2/\delta)}{N}} + \frac{M + \log(2/\delta)}{N} \right). \quad (11)$$

Expanding (8), we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon &= \|\bar{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{R}^{-1} - \mathbf{I}\|_2 + \|(\widehat{\mathbf{R}} - \bar{\mathbf{R}})\mathbf{R}^{-1}\|_2 \\ &\leq \|\bar{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{R}^{-1} - \mathbf{I}\|_2 + \|(\widehat{\mathbf{R}} - \bar{\mathbf{R}})\|_2 \|\mathbf{R}^{-1}\|_2 \\ &\leq e^\rho - 1 + \|(\widehat{\mathbf{R}} - \bar{\mathbf{R}})\|_2 \|\bar{\mathbf{R}}^{-1}\|_2 e^\rho \\ &\leq e^\rho - 1 + \kappa(\bar{\mathbf{R}}) e^\rho \sqrt{\frac{M + \log(2/\delta)}{N}} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where we used the submultiplicativity of the operator norm for the first inequality, (9) and (10) for the second inequality, and (11) by discarding the lower-order linear term (negligible when $N \gg M$) in the last inequality.

Solving (12) for N yields the $N_0(\varepsilon, \delta, \rho)$ stated in the theorem.

Next, we use Taylor expansions and bound the absolute difference between the criteria.

Let $x = \lambda - 1$ with $|x| \leq \varepsilon < 1$. Note that:

$$\psi_{\text{AMV}}(x) = x^2, \quad (13)$$

And that

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{\text{SPICE}}(x) &= \left(\sqrt{1+x} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+x}} \right)^2 = \frac{x^2}{1+x} \\ &= x^2 - \frac{x^3}{x+1} \\ &= x^2 - x^3 + \frac{x^4}{1+x}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The 3-rd order Taylor expansion around zero of $\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(x)$ is by:

$$\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(x) = \log^2(1+x) = x^2 - x^3 + r_3^{(\text{AIRM})}(x), \quad (15)$$

with the remainder defined for some $\xi \in (0, x)$ by:

$$r_3^{(\text{AIRM})}(x) = x^4 \cdot \frac{11 - 6\log(1+\xi)}{12(1+\xi)^4}, \quad (16)$$

hence:

$$|r_3^{(\text{AIRM})}(x)| \leq \varepsilon^4 \cdot \frac{11 + 6|\log(1-\varepsilon)|}{12(1-\varepsilon)^4}. \quad (17)$$

To align the leading quadratic term with the other criteria, we develop the 3-rd order Taylor expansion around zero of $8\psi_{\text{JBLD}}(x)$. It is expressed by:

$$\begin{aligned} 8\psi_{\text{JBLD}}(x) &= 8\log\left(1 + \frac{x}{2}\right) - 4\log(1+x) \\ &= x^2 - x^3 + r_3^{(\text{JBLD})}(x) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

with the remainder defined for some $\xi \in (0, x)$ by:

$$r_3^{(\text{JBLD})}(x) = x^4 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{(\xi+1)^4} - \frac{1}{(\xi+2)^4} \right) \quad (19)$$

hence:

$$|r_3^{(\text{JBLD})}(x)| \leq \varepsilon^4 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{(1-\varepsilon)^4} + \frac{1}{(2-\varepsilon)^4} \right) \quad (20)$$

We now derive the per-eigenvalue bounds and then sum over m . Each of $\{\text{AMV}, \text{AIRM}, \text{JBLD}\}$ will be compared to SPICE criterion.

(i) AMV vs. SPICE:

Compute

$$|\psi_{\text{AMV}}(x) - \psi_{\text{SPICE}}(x)| = \left| \frac{x^3}{x+1} \right| \leq \varepsilon^3 \cdot \frac{1}{1-\varepsilon}.$$

Define $C_{\text{AMV}}(\varepsilon) = \frac{1}{1-\varepsilon}$, which converges to a finite constant when $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. Now, bounding criteria absolute difference using the triangle inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{D}_{\text{AMV}}^2 - \mathcal{D}_{\text{SPICE}}^2| &\leq \sum_m |\psi_{\text{AMV}}(\lambda_m) - \psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda_m)| \\ &\leq M \cdot C_{\text{AMV}}(\varepsilon) \cdot \varepsilon^3 \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

(ii) AIRM vs. SPICE:

Compute

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(x) - \psi_{\text{SPICE}}(x)| &= |r_3^{(\text{AIRM})}(x) - \frac{x^4}{x+1}| \\ &\leq \varepsilon^4 \cdot \left(\frac{11+6|\log(1-\varepsilon)|}{12(1-\varepsilon)^4} + \frac{1}{1-\varepsilon} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Define $C_{\text{AIRM}}(\varepsilon) = \left(\frac{11+6|\log(1-\varepsilon)|}{12(1-\varepsilon)^4} + \frac{1}{1-\varepsilon} \right)$, which converges to a finite constant when $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. Now, bounding criteria absolute difference using the triangle inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{D}_{\text{AIRM}}^2 - \mathcal{D}_{\text{SPICE}}^2| &\leq \sum_m |\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda_m) - \psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda_m)| \\ &\leq M \cdot C_{\text{AIRM}}(\varepsilon) \cdot \varepsilon^4 \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

(iii) JBLD vs. SPICE:

Compute

$$\begin{aligned} |8\psi_{\text{JBLD}}(x) - \psi_{\text{SPICE}}(x)| &= |r_3^{(\text{JBLD})}(x) - \frac{x^4}{x+1}| \\ &\leq \varepsilon^4 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{(1-\varepsilon)^4} + \frac{1}{(2-\varepsilon)^4} + \frac{1}{1-\varepsilon} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Define $C_{\text{JBLD}}(\varepsilon) = \left(\frac{1}{(1-\varepsilon)^4} + \frac{1}{(2-\varepsilon)^4} + \frac{1}{1-\varepsilon} \right)$, which converges to a finite constant when $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. Now, bounding criteria absolute difference using the triangle inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} |8\mathcal{D}_{\text{JBLD}}^2 - \mathcal{D}_{\text{SPICE}}^2| &\leq \sum_m |\psi_{\text{JBLD}}(\lambda_m) - \psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda_m)| \\ &\leq M \cdot C_{\text{JBLD}}(\varepsilon) \cdot \varepsilon^4 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Combining the bounds (i)–(iii) yields the stated inequalities, which completes the proof. \square

4 Proof of Theorem 2 (Criteria robustness to eigenvalue deviations)

Theorem 2 (Criteria robustness to eigenvalue deviations). *Suppose that for some $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ all but one of the eigenvalues of \mathbf{Q} remain close to 1, i.e. $|\lambda_m - 1| \leq \varepsilon$ for all $m \neq r$, while a single eigenvalue can be expressed as $\lambda_r = 1 + \Delta$, with Δ dominant in logarithmic scale:*

$$\log(1 + \Delta) \geq \max\{\log(1 + \varepsilon), -\log(1 - \varepsilon)\}.$$

Define the relative contribution of λ_r under criterion \bullet as

$$s_r^{(\bullet)} = \frac{\psi_{\bullet}(\lambda_r)}{\sum_{m=1}^M \psi_{\bullet}(\lambda_m)}.$$

Then

$$s_r^{(\text{AMV})} \geq s_r^{(\text{SPICE})} \geq s_r^{(\text{AIRM})} \geq s_r^{(\text{JBLD})}.$$

Proof.

To exploit monotonicity, we work in the log–eigenvalue coordinates:

$$u_m \triangleq \frac{1}{2} \log \lambda_m$$

so that $\lambda_m = e^{2u_m}$. The scalar penalties in (3) can be written as functions of u :

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{\text{AMV}}(\lambda) &= (e^{2u} - 1)^2, & \psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda) &= 4 \sinh^2 u, \\ \psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda) &= 4u^2, & \psi_{\text{JBLD}}(\lambda) &= \log(\cosh u). \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Denote $U_{\max} \triangleq \frac{1}{2} \max\{\log(1 + \varepsilon), -\log(1 - \varepsilon)\}$. Notice that by theorem assumptions, for $m \neq r$:

$$|u_m| \leq U_{\max} \leq u_r.$$

Now, we derive a useful equivalence that will aid the proof.

Set for each criterion:

$$S^{(\bullet)} \triangleq \sum_{m \neq r} \psi_{\bullet}(\lambda_m). \quad (25)$$

Observe that $\psi_{\bullet}(\lambda) \geq 0$ for all criteria, which can be verified algebraically and is illustrated in Figure 1 of the main manuscript. Consequently, $S^{(\bullet)} \geq 0$ holds for all criteria.

For any two criteria A and B , $s_r^{(A)} \leq s_r^{(B)} \iff \frac{\psi_A(\lambda_r)}{S^{(A)}} \leq \frac{\psi_B(\lambda_r)}{S^{(B)}}$. Equivalently,

$$s_r^{(A)} \leq s_r^{(B)} \iff \frac{S^{(B)}}{S^{(A)}} \leq \frac{\psi_B(\lambda_r)}{\psi_A(\lambda_r)}. \quad (26)$$

with the convention that if $S^{(A)} = S^{(B)} = 0$ then $s_r^{(A)} = s_r^{(B)} = 1$ and the inequality holds with equality.

Next, we show two monotonicity lemmas on the log–scale.

Observe the following two lemmas.

(L1) For $u \in \mathbb{R}$, define the ratio:

$$\alpha(u) \triangleq \frac{\psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda)}{\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda)} = \left(\frac{\sinh u}{u} \right)^2, \text{ with } \alpha(0) \triangleq 1.$$

Then $\alpha(u)$ is strictly increasing in $|u|$.

Proof.

For $u > 0$, define $f(u) = \sinh u/u$. Then, $f'(u) = \frac{u \cosh u - \sinh u}{u^2}$. The numerator $g(u) = u \cosh u - \sinh u$ satisfies $g'(u) = u \sinh u > 0$ and $g(0) = 0$, so $g(u) > 0$ for $u > 0$. Hence $f'(u) > 0$ and $\alpha(u) = f(u)^2$ increases on $u > 0$. Notice that $\alpha(u)$ is an even function, hence $\alpha(u)$ increases in $|u|$.

(L2) For $u \in \mathbb{R}$, define the ratio:

$$\beta(u) \triangleq \frac{\psi_{\text{JBLD}}(\lambda)}{\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda)} = \frac{\log(\cosh u)}{4u^2}, \text{ with } \beta(0) \triangleq 1/8.$$

Then $\beta(u)$ is strictly decreasing in $|u|$.

Proof.

For $u > 0$, $\beta'(u) = \frac{u \tanh u - 2 \log(\cosh u)}{4u^3}$. Define the numerator $h(u) \triangleq u \tanh u - 2 \log(\cosh u)$. We got $h'(u) = u \operatorname{sech}^2 u - \tanh u$ and $h''(u) = -2u \cdot \operatorname{sech}^2 u \cdot \tanh u$. For $u > 0$, $h''(u)$ is negative, and $h'(0) = 0$, it follows that $h'(u) < 0$. Hence, for $u > 0$, $h(u)$ is strictly decreasing with $h(0) = 0$, so $h(u) < 0$ and thus $\beta'(u) < 0$. Notice that $\beta(u)$ is an even function, hence β decreases in $|u|$.

We are now ready to prove the following inequalities

$$(i) \frac{s_r^{(\text{AMV})}}{\geq s_r^{(\text{SPICE})}}:$$

Notice that

$$\psi_{\text{AMV}}(\lambda_m) = (\lambda_m - 1)^2 = \lambda_m \left(\sqrt{\lambda_m} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda_m}} \right)^2 = \lambda_m \psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda_m),$$

for all m . Hence

$$\frac{S^{(\text{AMV})}}{S^{(\text{SPICE})}} = \frac{\sum_{m \neq r} \lambda_m \psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda_m)}{\sum_{m \neq r} \psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda_m)} \leq \max_{m \neq r} \lambda_m \leq \lambda_r,$$

since, $\max_{m \neq r} \lambda_m \leq 1 + \varepsilon \leq 1 + \Delta = \lambda_r$.

Therefore,

$$\frac{S^{(\text{AMV})}}{S^{(\text{SPICE})}} \leq \lambda_r = \frac{\psi_{\text{AMV}}(\lambda_r)}{\psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda_r)},$$

and by (26) (with $B = \text{AMV}$, $A = \text{SPICE}$) we conclude $s_r^{(\text{AMV})} \geq s_r^{(\text{SPICE})}$.

$$(ii) \frac{s_r^{(\text{SPICE})}}{\geq s_r^{(\text{AIRM})}}:$$

For each $m \neq r$, by (L1), evenness of $\alpha(u)$ and $|u_m| \leq U_{\max} \leq u_r$:

$$\frac{\psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda_m)}{\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda_m)} = \alpha(u_m) = \alpha(|u_m|) \leq \alpha(u_r) = \frac{\psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda_r)}{\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda_r)}.$$

Multiplying by $\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda_m) \geq 0$ and summing over $m \neq r$ yields

$$S^{(\text{SPICE})} \leq \frac{\psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda_r)}{\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda_r)} S^{(\text{AIRM})}.$$

Equivalently (for non-degenerate case where $S^{(\text{AIRM})} > 0$):

$$\frac{S^{(\text{SPICE})}}{S^{(\text{AIRM})}} \leq \frac{\psi_{\text{SPICE}}(\lambda_r)}{\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda_r)}.$$

Applying (26) (with $B = \text{SPICE}$, $A = \text{AIRM}$) gives $s_r^{(\text{SPICE})} \geq s_r^{(\text{AIRM})}$.

(iii) $s_r^{(\text{AIRM})} \geq s_r^{(\text{JBLD})}$:

For each $m \neq r$, by (L2), evenness of $\beta(u)$ and $|u_m| \leq U_{\max} \leq u_r$:

$$\frac{\psi_{\text{JBLD}}(\lambda_m)}{\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda_m)} = \beta(u_m) = \beta(|u_m|) \geq \beta(u_r) = \frac{\psi_{\text{JBLD}}(\lambda_r)}{\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda_r)}.$$

Multiplying by $\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda_m) \geq 0$ and summing over $m \neq r$ gives

$$S^{(\text{JBLD})} \geq \frac{\psi_{\text{JBLD}}(\lambda_r)}{\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda_r)} S^{(\text{AIRM})}.$$

Equivalently,

$$\frac{S^{(\text{JBLD})}}{S^{(\text{AIRM})}} \geq \frac{\psi_{\text{JBLD}}(\lambda_r)}{\psi_{\text{AIRM}}(\lambda_r)}.$$

Applying (26) (with $B = \text{AIRM}$, $A = \text{JBLD}$) yields $s_r^{(\text{AIRM})} \geq s_r^{(\text{JBLD})}$.

Combining (i),(ii) and (iii) concludes the proof. \square

References

- [1] R. Vershynin, *High-Dimensional Probability: An Introduction with Applications in Data Science*, Cambridge University Press, 2018.